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Reconfigurable control system for machine tools with a switchable kinematic and variable execution flow of the kinematic algorithm

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Abstract

This paper introduces the development of a control system for reconfigurable machine tools, featuring switchable kinematics and a variable execution flow of kinematic algorithms. The research highlights the importance of a low-cost, adaptable solution for retrofitting aging CNC machinery, enhancing their flexibility and modularity. By leveraging open-architecture platforms like LinuxCNC, the system incorporates direct and inverse kinematic functions designed to support multiple kinematic configurations without necessitating axis reinitialization or workpiece repositioning. Validated through real-world experiments, the proposed system offers significant benefits for both educational and research purposes.

Keywords

Reconfigurable control systems, CNC machine tools, Kinematic algorithms, LinuxCNC

1. INTRODUCTION

Modern manufacturing faces conflicting demands: increasing productivity, flexibility, and performance while maintaining or enhancing quality. Achieving these goals within the framework of Industry 4.0 points to reconfigurable machine tools, classified in the literature [1] into two levels of reconfigurability: fully or partially reconfigurable.

The full reconfigurability of a machine tool allows processing of the workpiece using different kinematic configurations without the need for reinitializing axes or repositioning the workpiece within the usable workspace. The fact that full reconfigurability implies the ability to

change the kinematic structure of the machine leads to the development of control systems with encapsulated kinematic functions, making machine operation intuitive and accessible to users. Using machines capable of changing their structure and operating characteristics without adequate solutions in the control system can lead to numerous problems.

Developing control systems for reconfigurable machine tools is a complex task requiring a multidisciplinary approach. One frequently used method is 'virtual commissioning' [2,3], which leverages digital twin technology [4]. This approach is integral to the Industry 4.0 paradigm and cyber-physical systems (CPS) [5]. The objective is to finalize the development of control functions within a digital environment, enabling the validation of algorithms without risk to the actual machine or its surroundings. Subsequently, the system was implemented on the machine in a production setting for final verification and performance testing.

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The need for an accessible control system capable of implementing complex kinematic algorithms, demanding sequential control functions, and customizable user interfaces pointed to the development of a software-oriented CNC based on LinuxCNC software tools and open-architecture computing hardware.

2. RECONFIGURABLE MACHINE TOOL

The paper examines cases where changes in the kinematic structure of the machine are induced by external factors, beyond of the control system. In other words, it explores scenarios involving machine tools where the reconfigurability is achieved manually or with the help of suitable hydraulic or motor drives, through repositioning of the working axes. In such cases, the tool orientation can either change, with this information contained in the tool table, or remain unchanged, with information about the change in machine configuration specified in a redefined M instruction invoked during program execution.

A characteristic example of a reconfigurable machine tool is provided in the work of [6]. (2004), where a non-orthogonal reconfigurable machine tool is described (see Fig. 1). The study also proposes a method for controlling such reconfigurable machine tools, relying on two cross-coupling (CC) controllers. In this context, changes in the kinematic structure are observed as path deviations relative to standard orthogonal machine configurations, which need to be compensated for. Compensation was conducted in two directions: correction of contour error in the xy plane and depth adjustment along the tool axis z. This approach is elaborated in greater detail in the work of [6].

The EMCO F1 CNC is an educational 3-axis machine, equipped with a milling head that can be manually swiveled 90 degrees horizontally or vertically (Fig. 2). During retrofitting and control system upgrades, the EMCO F1 was identified as a reconfigurable machine tool. It served as a testbed to validate the proposed theory on switchable kinematics and the variable execution flow of kinematic functions. The results of these experiments are detailed in the paper.

Fig. 1. Non-orthogonal reconfigurable machine tool [6]

Fig. 2. EMCO F1 – Educational 3-axis vertical/horizontal milling machine recognized as reconfigurable machine tool

3. SWITCHABLE KINEMATICS CONTROL SYSTEM OR KINEMATIC FUNCTION WITH VARIABLE EXECUTION FLOW

In order to efficiently utilize existing CAD/CAM systems for programming the aforementioned reconfigurable machine tools, the paper proposes the implementation of a kinematic algorithm with variable execution flow on a single control system, which would encompass all kinematic configurations of a reconfigurable machine tool.

Although the machine reconfiguration is conducted manually, dictated by machining requirements, it is initiated through a corresponding M instruction or tool change instruction, during which the tool's orientation is changed. In practical terms, transitioning from one kinematic configuration to another is equivalent to switching from one machine tool to another. As such, it would require repositioning the workpiece, initializing the machine, and determining the reference coordinate system of the workpiece, i.e., setting up G54–G59.3 instructions in the control system. These steps are also essential for reconfigurable machine tools equipped with a single control system featuring multiple control configurations, implemented for each kinematic configuration of the machine.

Control algorithms need to be extended with direct and inverse kinematics functions that allow for variable execution flow following directives obtained from the tool table or the control program, i.e., the machining program.

Based on the presented problem, and intending to develop a reconfigurable control unit with variable execution flow for the kinematic algorithm, the requirements set for the research and development team were as follows:

- **To utilize standard CAD/CAM systems for machine programming**, adhering to conventions for machine tool axis labeling and orientation.
- **To develop a virtual environment for machining program simulation**, ensuring collision detection and elimination between the machine and the workpiece, as well as among the machine's moving parts.
- **To make the user interface intuitive**, with all necessary functions for the safe operation of the machine.

In line with the requirement for managing a machine with a variable kinematic structure, it

was necessary to develop a software framework to enable the subsequent implementation of inverse and direct kinematics functions for all kinematic configurations of a specific reconfigurable machine tool. Special attention was needed in defining the kinematic model, adopting internal coordinate vectors tied to machine axes for all kinematic configurations. This approach allows for the dynamic reconfigurability of the control system in later implementations.

When the machine's kinematic configuration changes, the adopted vectors adjust their position and direction according to the changes in the positions and orientations of the machine axes. However, these changes will not affect the scalar values of the internal coordinates, thus avoiding the need for reinitialization, as shown in Fig. 3, with example values of q_1 , q_2 , and q_3 .

During implementation, communication mechanisms for the software kinematics module, which runs in real time, must interact with the information processing system from the machining program and/or external sensor data. This task is hardware- and software-dependent and mostly implementable on open architecture systems.

Fig. 3. Example of kinematic transformation of a reconfigurable machine tool EMCO F1

The template algorithm of the kinematic module, which includes elements for signaling changes in execution flow, as well as space for implementing multiple kinematic functions according to the machine's configuration kinematic models, is shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. Example of switchable kinematics function of a reconfigurable machine tool

4. IMPLEMENTATION

As mentioned, EMCO F1 is recognized as a reconfigurable milling machine for retrofitting and improving the control system. As a 3-axis machine, it is a testbed for proving the presented methodology. The milling head can be manually rotated 90 degrees to a horizontal or vertical position. A quick-change tool system is present, but the tool change is manual. The machine is programmed using the ISO 6983 standard, i.e., the language known as G-code. Two machining programs were used for vertical and horizontal machines with different machine reference points and control system configurations. As originally designed, the machine could operate as a vertical or horizontal milling machine by manually rotating the milling head, starting the appropriate control system configuration, and initializing all axes. For a machine tool with recognized reconfigurable characteristics, it was necessary to develop a control system based on open architecture software to fulfil the idea. LinuxCNC, widely used software for controlling machine tools and robots, has been chosen as a development platform for implementing switchable kinematics.

The idea was to use the tool's angle orientation information from the tool table to detect machine tool reconfiguration requests while interpreting the G-code program. The intention was to perform the entire reconfiguration

process without restarting the machine, using the appropriate workpiece coordinate systems G54, G55, etc., for the horizontal and vertical machine configurations. The kinematic modeling approach assumes a consistent orientation of joint vectors across all configurations to satisfy the specified requirements. In other words, the rotation of axes during kinematic transformations does not alter the positions of the joint vectors associated with the axes. Consequently, the scalar values of joint vectors remain unchanged, eliminating the need for reinitialization.

Analytical solutions of direct and inverse kinematics are relatively trivial. The initial machine configuration and the adopted global coordinates determine the form of the kinematic transformation.

If the vertical configuration of the machine is the initial point of reconfiguration, which is considered trivial kinematics where the joint coordinates $q = [q_1 \ q_2 \ q_3]^T$ are identical to the external coordinates $x = [x_1 \ x_2 \ x_3]^T$, the solutions for direct and inverse kinematics are:

$$\begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} q_1 \\ q_2 \\ q_3 \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

The following equation (2) defines the transition from the vertical to the horizontal configuration of the milling machine:

$$\begin{bmatrix} q_1 \\ q_2 \\ q_3 \end{bmatrix} = R_z(90^\circ) \cdot R_x(90^\circ) \cdot \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} z \\ x \\ y \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

The previous equation defines the direct and inverse kinematics for the horizontal configuration of the milling machine.

The following equation (3) defines the transition from the horizontal to the vertical configuration of the milling machine:

$$\begin{bmatrix} q_1 \\ q_2 \\ q_3 \end{bmatrix} = R_x(-90^\circ) \cdot R_z(-90^\circ) \cdot \begin{bmatrix} z \\ x \\ y \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} z \\ x \\ y \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

LinuxCNC integrates direct and inverse kinematics functions and allows for simple modifications of control configurations. Thus, it is ideal for controlling standard and specialized tool machine configurations. The following steps are necessary to configure LinuxCNC software for controlling a 3-axis CNC milling machine:

1. Creating a directory containing all configuration files for the machine;

2. Generating configuration (*.ini) files defines the machine's basic parameters, including axis ranges, maximum speeds, accelerations for each axis, real-time system parameters, and more;
3. Creating configuration (*.hal) files with information related to motion control for both the physical and virtual machines;
4. Configuring the control system's hardware, focusing on implementing appropriate interfaces between actuators and their corresponding drivers.

During the tool change procedure, the axes are first repositioned to eliminate collisions between the machine's moving parts and the workpieces. The operator is signalled to change the tool manually and the Z-axis orientation if necessary. The reconfiguration procedure is manual on the real machine, but fully automatic from a control system point of view. It is allowed by adding rotary axis B, as shown in Fig. 5, within the switching inverse kinematics function.

Fig. 5. The algorithm of the inverse kinematics function for EMCO F1 machine tool

When the M6 function is called in the machining program, the Hardware Abstraction Layer (HAL) variable of control software `*(haldata->tool_offset_b)` is initialized with the tool orientation value from the tool table. The variable `*(haldata->tool_offset_b)` carries a decision value that is used to switch the flow of the kinematics function.

5. EXPERIMENTS

The workpiece for experimental testing of the control system was designed based on an

example for evaluating the accuracy of CNC machine tools. This part was modified and prepared for machining in two planes to match the dimensions of the machine's working space. The illustration of the machined part in two planes during testing is shown in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. Experimental testing of the developed control system

Figure 6a illustrates the final machined part with the main spindle in a vertical position. The main

spindle was then reconfigured to a horizontal position, as shown in Figure 6b, while Figure 6c displays the final machined part with the spindle in a horizontal position. The machining test was conducted on wooden material using a flat milling tool with a diameter of 6 mm.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The paper presents an approach to the development of a reconfigurable control system with switchable kinematic functions.

The developed system is suitable for retrofitting and modernizing old CNC machine tools, representing a low-cost and fast solution. Due to the suggested control system's modularity, flexibility, availability, and openness, reconfigurable machine tools are particularly suitable for implementing the proposed system. The proposed control system's modularity, flexibility, openness, and availability make it ideal for machine implementation with reconfigurable kinematics and unique functionalities. The developed control system has been successfully designed, validated, and prototyped through real-world machine experiments. The subject machine is used for research and education at the Faculty of Forestry, University of Belgrade.

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